

ADVANTAGES OF PROSTATE-SPECIFIC ANTIGEN TESTING IN REDUCING MORTALITY FROM PROSTATE CANCER

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Abstract. *The diagnosis of many forms of prostate cancer is often based on the detection of elevated levels of prostate-specific antigen in the blood (above 4 ng/mL). However, to confirm the diagnosis of prostate cancer, a tissue biopsy is usually performed. The presented data indicate that the distribution of prostate-specific antigen levels and prostate volume between the study groups was comparable across most value intervals, which may suggest homogeneity of the studied populations in terms of these parameters.*

Keywords: *Prostate cancer, prostate-specific antigen, overactive bladder syndrome.*

Annotatsiya. *Prostata bezi saratonining ko‘plab shakllarini aniqlashda ko‘pincha qonda prostataning o‘ziga xos antigen miqdorining oshishi (4 ng/ml dan yuqori) asosida amalga oshiriladi. Biroq, prostata bezi saratonini tasdiqlash uchun odatda to‘qimalar biopsiyasi o‘tkaziladi. Taqdim etilgan ma‘lumotlarga ko‘ra, prostataning o‘ziga xos antigen darajasi va prostata bezi hajmining tadqiqot guruhlarida orasidagi taqsimoti aksariyat hollarda qiymat oraliqlari bo‘yicha yaqin bo‘lib, bu parametrlar shu nuqtai nazaridan o‘rganilgan populyatsiyalar bir xilligini ko‘rsatishi mumkin.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *Prostata bezi saratoni, prostataning o‘ziga xos antigen, giperfaol qovuq sindromi.*

Аннотация. *Диагноз многих форм рака простаты часто основывается на обнаружении повышенных уровней простатического специфического антигена в крови (более 4 нг/мл). Однако для подтверждения диагноза рака предстательной железы обычно проводится биопсия тканей. На основании представленных данных установлено, что распределение уровней простатспецифического антигена и объема предстательной железы в сравниваемых группах исследования оказалось сопоставимым по большинству интервалов. Это указывает на однородность изучаемых популяций с точки зрения данных параметров*

Ключевые слова: *Рак простаты, простатспецифический антиген, синдром гиперактивного мочевого пузыря.*

Introduction. The increase in incidence in developing countries is associated with both increased life expectancy and improved access to medical care. The rise in incidence is also due to the westernisation of lifestyles, including obesity, sedentary lifestyles and dietary factors [1;2].

Global variations in prostate cancer incidence may be related to differences between countries in PSA testing. For example, in Europe, prostate cancer is the most common cancer among men, accounting for 24% of all new cases in 2018, with an estimated 450,000 new cases [3]. In the United States, prostate cancer ranks second in prevalence, accounting for 9.5% of all new cancer cases (with 164,690 new cases in 2018). Recent studies show that 20 to 40% of

prostate cancer cases in the United States and Europe may be associated with excessive testing for prostate-specific antigen [4].

Despite significant scientific advances in understanding the molecular mechanisms and risk factors associated with prostate cancer, this type of cancer remains the second leading cause of death among men in the United States. International data on prostate cancer mortality show significant differences around the world [5]. High mortality rates were reported in Central America (10.7 per 100,000 people), Australia, New Zealand, and Western Europe, while countries in Asia (3.3) and North Africa (5.8) had lower rates.

With regard to prostate cancer prevention, the US Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) recommends prostate-specific antigen screening for men aged 55-69, seeing a potential benefit in reducing mortality from this type of cancer.

However, for men over 70, the effectiveness of screening is less convincing [6].

At the same time, prostate cancer mortality rates in many Western countries, including North America, Western and Northern Europe, are steadily declining. This decline may be due to both early detection and improved treatment methods [7].

Recent studies in the United States, although not demonstrating the benefits of prostate-specific antigen testing in reducing prostate cancer mortality, unlike the European study, have revealed differences in the effectiveness of this screening method [8].

Prostate cancer is traditionally diagnosed by digital rectal examination and analysis of prostate-specific antigen levels in the blood, followed by biopsy under transrectal ultrasound guidance [9].

However, with the widespread use of prostate-specific antigen tests and the introduction of screening programmes, more than 60% of prostate cancer cases are detected in patients who have no symptoms and whose digital rectal examination results were normal, but who were found to have elevated prostate-specific antigen levels [10].

The diagnosis of many forms of prostate cancer is often based on the detection of elevated PSA levels in the blood (more than 4 ng/ml). However, a tissue biopsy is usually performed to confirm the diagnosis of prostate cancer [9].

To date, transrectal ultrasound-guided prostate biopsy remains the gold standard for diagnosis in various clinical scenarios for confirming prostate cancer [11].

The diagnosis of many forms of prostate cancer is often based on the detection of elevated levels of prostate-specific antigen in the blood (more than 4 ng/ml). However, tissue biopsy is usually performed to confirm the diagnosis of prostate cancer [9].

Materials and methods. The material for the study was collected as part of a clinical study at the Republican Specialised Scientific and Practical Medical Centre for Oncology and Radiology of the Samarkand Branch and the Samarkand Regional Interregional Hospice from 2020 to 2025. The basic dataset included information on patients diagnosed with prostate cancer and concomitant urological pathology in the form of bladder hyperactivity.

Type of study:

Prospective, randomised, controlled clinical trial.

Study participants:

Main group: 75 patients with prostate cancer undergoing comprehensive supportive therapy for comorbid urological pathology (overactive bladder syndrome) in the form of physical exercises to strengthen the pelvic floor muscles in combination with combined drug therapy against the background of androgen deprivation therapy at the Republican Specialised Scientific

-practical medical centre for oncology and radiology of the Samarkand branch of the Samarkand Regional Interregional Hospice.

Control group: 65 patients with prostate cancer undergoing comprehensive supportive therapy for comorbid urological pathology (overactive bladder syndrome) in the form of combined drug therapy for overactive bladder syndrome against the background of androgen deprivation therapy, treated at the Republican Specialised Scientific and Practical Medical Centre for Oncology and Radiology, Samarkand Branch, and the Samarkand Regional Interregional Hospice.

The androgen deprivation therapy group without overactive bladder syndrome therapy consisted of 40 people treated at the Republican Specialised Scientific and Practical Medical Centre for Oncology and Radiology, Samarkand Branch, Samarkand Regional Interregional Hospice.

Inclusion criteria:

Confirmed diagnosis of prostate cancer. No metastases to distant organs. Signed informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion criteria:

Presence of other oncological diseases. Previous history of allergy to components of adjuvant therapy.

Study conduct:

Randomisation of patients into three groups. Determination of primary and secondary baseline indicators. Regular monitoring and assessment of patient status using appropriate scales and tools. Collection of data on length of hospital stay.

Recording of recurrence and overall survival throughout the study.

Results and discussion: A comparative study was conducted to analyse prostate-specific antigen levels and prostate volume in patients included in the study.

pic. 1. **Prostate cancer** (general)

More than 50 ng/ml of prostate-specific antigen were found in 4 (6.2%) patients in the main group, 4 (7.3%) in the control group, and 1 (3.3%) in the group receiving androgen deprivation therapy without treatment for overactive bladder.

Statistical analysis showed that the differences between the groups in terms of prostate-specific antigen levels were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

The mean prostate volumes were also similar between groups, at 67 ± 35 cm³ for the main group, 66 ± 41 cm³ for the control group, and 64 ± 34 cm³ for the androgen deprivation therapy without overactive bladder therapy group, with no statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$). .

The data presented indicate that the distribution of prostate-specific antigen levels and prostate volume between the study groups was comparable in most value intervals, which may indicate the homogeneity of the study populations in terms of these parameters.

Conclusions: The study revealed a significant decrease in prostate-specific antigen levels from 16.06 ± 9.42 to 6.03 ± 3.71 and a reduction in prostate volume from 67 ± 35.4 to 36.6 ± 8.5 ($p < 0.05$) in the main group after 6 months of complex therapy, including androgen deprivation therapy, medication, and physical exercise, highlighting the effectiveness of this approach in the treatment of prostate cancer and overactive bladder.

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